

Assessment of marine litter barrier initiatives and their potential as a prevention strategy in Brazil

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Supplementary Material

Questionnaire: Ecobarrier and Ecoboat litter removal initiatives

Blue Keepers is a program developed to combat plastic pollution in rivers and the ocean, in a systemic and lasting way. Within the scope of our actions, Phase 2 of the project aims to work with Emergency Actions to contain and remove this waste through coordination in municipalities, mobilization of resources, planning and systematization of campaigns aimed at these actions, evaluation of actions and data obtained, and communication of the results.

To this end, we from the Blue Keepers team are seeking to identify initiatives in Brazilian territory to remove plastic waste in marine, estuarine and river environments using the Ecobarriers and/or Ecoboat technique (or equivalent) in order to obtain an overview of the maturity of initiatives, operation, effectiveness and bottlenecks.

Ecobarriers are floating structures installed across the channel of bodies of water to retain floating waste in order to facilitate collection and more appropriate disposal.

Ecoboats are vessels that collect floating waste in bodies of water, using either manual or automated techniques, in order to carry out the most appropriate disposal.

Your contribution is very important to our work towards a cleaner and healthier environment!

Question 1: Name of the initiative you represent.

Question 2: E-mail for contact.

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Question 3: Telephone.

Question 4: Website, if available.

Question 5: Social networks, if available (Instagram, Facebook, LinkedIn, etc).

Question 6: State where the initiative is located.

Question 7: Municipality where the initiative is located.

Question 8: Environment and location where the initiative operates. (e.g.: mouth of the Jequitinhonha River)

Question 9: Describe the structure of the operation (e.g.: dimension, covered area, team involved, etc).

Question 10: What is the level of maturity of this initiative?

Initial phase: Planned/Being planned

Initial phase: Raising funds for implementation

Advanced phase: Implemented/In follow-up

Advanced phase: Raising funds for maintenance

Other: _____

Question 11: How long has the initiative been active (since its first removal action) and how many actions have taken place?

Question 12: Which partnerships enable the operation?

Question 13: What are the indicators used? (amount or weight of litter removed, time in operation, waste composition, etc.). Could you present an annual estimate?

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Question 14: General financial operating cost per action (specify how long a removal action takes and what human resources and materials are used).

Question 15: What are current demands for the maintenance of the action in regard to financial and human resources, infrastructure, and other aspects. What is necessary for the initiative to continue?

Question 16: Please leave any questions or comments that you believe are relevant.